

Effect of Hygroscopic Aging on the Transverse Damage Behavior of Fiber-Reinforced Composites: A Computational Micromechanics Study

K V Vaishakh¹, N K Parambil², Vikas Srivastava¹

¹ School of Engineering, Brown University

² Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware

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Introduction

- FRP composite: heterogeneous phase of fiber and polymeric matrix
- Application: Aerospace, Marine, and Wind turbine blades
- Exposure to extreme environments

Hygrothermal exposure

- Synergetic effects of water and temperature
- No effect on fiber
- Matrix undergoes chemical and physical changes
- Mechanical properties of composite deteriorate

Background

- Material: Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional laminates
- Tests: Diffusion at various temp
- Void characterization: micro-CT scan.

- Unaged: no pores (voids)
- With water ingress porosity increases
- Void formation along the fiber at the interface

Background

- Atomistic analysis of the hygrothermal effect on carbon fiber epoxy interface.
- Water molecules drastically deteriorate the integrity of the carbon fiber/epoxy interface.
- Elevated temperature level further degrades the interfacial mechanical response.

Motivation and Objective

- Many studies on the influence of void on mechanical properties
- Either inter-fiber voids or matrix voids
- How process-induced voids influence the water ingress in the specimen

Objective

- Systematic study of interface voids
- Develop a correlation: Moisture-induced porosity with water content in the specimen

Void types [1]

FE geometry and Modeling details

Composite: Fiber, matrix, fiber/matrix interface, void (pore)

RVE

FE mesh

- Fiber vol fraction (v_f) is maintained at 0.56
- Periodic boundary condition (PBC) is applied at the boundaries
- RVE loading: a tensile strain of 1%
- Post processing: homogenized stress-strain curve

Parameters considered in the study:

1. Porosity (p in %) through $r_v = [0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9]$
2. Location of the pore (Θ) = $[0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ]$
3. Relative position of pore = [interface, matrix]

$$r_v = \sqrt{\frac{2p}{v_f}} r_f$$

Material model

Fiber: elastic material

Matrix: elasto-plastic

- Matrix: pressure-dependent yielding [1]

$$\Phi(\sigma, \sigma_c, \sigma_t) = 6J_2 + 2I_1(\sigma_c - \sigma_t) - 2\sigma_c\sigma_t$$

- Hardening law: saturation hardening: $\sigma = \sigma_y + (\sigma_s - \sigma_y) \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{H\epsilon^p}{(\sigma_s - \sigma_y)}\right)$

Dry and wet material properties of epoxy matrix

Condition	E (GPa)	σ_{yt} (MPa)	σ_{st} (MPa)	H_t (MPa)	σ_{yc} (MPa)	σ_{sc} (MPa)	H_c (MPa)
Dry	3.10	45	83	6500	66	126	6500
Wet	2.99	27	64	6500	40	104	6500

Matrix material (epoxy) response

Material model

Fiber/matrix interface:

- Cohesive interface with mixed-mode damage evolution

Interface properties [1, 2]

Property Description	Value
Stiffness	
K_c (N/mm ³)	10 ⁸
Maximum strength	
σ_n^0 (MPa)	54
τ_T^0 (MPa)	81 (1.5 σ_n^0)
τ_L^0 (MPa)	81 (1.5 σ_n^0)
Critical energy release rate	
G_{Ic} (N/mm)	0.002
G_{IIc} (N/mm)	0.1
G_{IIIc} (N/mm)	0.1
$G_s = G_{IIc} + G_{IIIc}$	
$G_t = G_{Ic} + G_{IIc}$	
Parameter in the BK law, m	1.45

Effect of porosity on strength

Effect of size

Effect of orientation

Effect of position

- Unexposed: no pores (voids)
- As porosity increases strength of the specimen decreases
- As $\theta \uparrow$ strength \rightarrow no pore strength
- Matrix porosity has a marginal effect on the strength.

Contours of stress and plastic strain

- Interface void: High stress concentration and intense plastic strain
- Matrix void: Near-void contours differ

Void-moisture relationship

Strength prediction and comparison

- Experimental result are within the lower and upper bounds predicted by simulations

Different approach: Probabilistic interface properties

- Strength of porous RVE: lower and upper bound
- Each interface: a probabilistic strength values (σ_x^0)
- Based on percentage reduction of lower and upper bound the

$$\sigma_{\min}^0 \leq \sigma_x^0 \leq \sigma_{\max}^0$$

- Distribution: Random and Softmin

Softmin distribution
$$p(x_i) = \frac{\exp(-x_i)}{\sum_j \exp(-x_j)}$$

Conclusions and future direction

- Interface void substantially influence the stress and strain distribution within the specimen
- Porosity of as small as 0.1% resulted in 15% reduction in strength
- Strength seems to depend on pore size, its orientation and location. The maximum impact is when void is at the interface and aligned along the loading direction ($\theta = 0^\circ$)
- A different probability-based approach to overcome the modeling complexity

Future work

- Coupled diffusion damage model for the interface and matrix material (polymer)
- Meso-scale modeling to predict the toughness of aged laminates

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Thank you!